

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

PROBEFIELD

A novel protocol for robust in-field monitoring of carbon stock and soil fertility based on proximal sensors and existing soil spectral libraries

Deliverable 4.3

A fieldwork protocol and procedures for cost-benefit estimation for using proximal soil sensing methods

Due date of deliverable: 57

Actual submission date: 15.11.2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Programme title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Programme website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Project title: ProbeField

Project website: <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/probefield>

Start date of the project: November 1st, 2021

Project duration: 36 months

Name of lead contractor: SLU

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	4.3
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	A fieldwork protocol and procedures for cost-benefit estimation for using proximal soil sensing methods
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP4
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Providing basis for selection of methods for point and 3D field estimation of soil properties
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	Roberto Barbetti, CREA
AUTHOR:	Carlos Lozano Fondón ^a , Maria Fantappiè ^a , Roberto Barbetti ^b , Melis Özge Pinar ^c , Sevinç Madenoglu ^c , Fabio Castaldi ^d , Romina Lorenzetti ^d , Bo Stenberg ^e , Konrad Metzger ^f , Luboš Borůvka ^g , Vahid Khosravi ^g , Dennis Walvoort ^h , Dik Pim ^h , Rafael López Núñez ⁱ , José A. Cayuela ⁱ , Triven Koganti ^j , Fenny van Egmond ^h

- a) Research Centre for Agriculture and Environment, Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, via di Lanciola 12/A, 50125 Florence, Italy
- b) Research Centre for Forest and Wood, Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, strada Frassineto, 35, 15033 Casale Monferrato, Alessandria, Italy
- c) General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies (TAGEM) Ankara, Turkey
- d) National Research Council (CNR) Firenze Italy
- e) Department of Soil and Environment, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Skara, Sweden
- f) Agroscope, Field-Crop Systems and Plant Nutrition, Route de Duillier 60, 1260, Nyon, Switzerland
- g) Department of Soil Science and Soil Protection, Faculty of Agrobiology, Food and Natural Resources, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Prague, Czech Republic
- h) Wageningen University and Research, the Netherlands
- i) Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)
- j) Department of Agroecology, Aarhus University, Blichers Alle 20, 8830 Tjele, Denmark

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14214678>

LICENSE CC BY 4.0

DISSEMINATION LEVEL: PU

ABSTRACT

The general objective of this protocol is to compare the results of spatializing soil properties as predicted by Proximal Soil Sensors (PSS) used by the ProbeField partners. It also aims to establish a standard methodology for conducting field experiments and analyzing the data.

Specifically, this protocol aims to provide I) insights about soil sampling design using covariates for the areas of interest; II) evaluate the suitability of measurements by applying protocols in the field during the PSS surveys; III) interpolation approaches to create baseline maps and IV) insights into the accuracies attainable using single versus combined PSS techniques, and incorporating data fusion with both linear and non-linear modeling approaches. Finally, we provide V) methods for evaluating the entire process of estimating soil properties in terms of costs and benefits. The last section of the document provides examples of new and historical case studies where the protocol has been applied and includes cost-benefit analysis.

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	5
1. Introduction.....	10
2. A Flow chart about how to decide on the activities.....	11
3. Slovenian case study: management-based sampling.....	17
3.1. Site description	17
3.2. Proximal soil sensing data and experimental design	17
3.3. Data preparation.....	18
3.4. Modeling of Point Measurements Using VNIR and XRF	19
3.5. Exploratory data analysis and modeling	19
3.6. Result: in-field multi-sensor system and accuracy variation	20
3.7. Result: estimation of properties with VNIR and XRF, and cost-benefit index application ..	22
4. Italian case study: regular grid sampling.....	22
4.1. Site description	22
4.2. Exploratory data analysis and modeling	23
4.3. Results: in-field multi-sensor system and accuracy variation.....	24
4.4. Result: estimation of properties with VNIR and XRF, and cost-benefit index application ..	26
5. Turkish case study: stratified random sampling	27
5.1. Site description	27
5.2. Exploratory data analysis and modeling	29
5.3. Results: in-field multi-sensor system and accuracy variation.....	32
5.4. Result: estimation of properties with VNIR and XRF, and cost-benefit index application ..	38
6. Dutch case study: Stratified Random and Random sampling (mixed strategy).....	39
6.1. Site description	39
6.2. Data Preparation.....	40
6.3. Exploratory data analysis and modeling	41
6.4. Results.....	42
7. Observations: Italian, Turkish, and Slovenian case studies.....	45
8. Example from other EJP SOIL-related projects	47
8.1. Czech Republic Case study: Conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling	47
8.1.1. Site description.....	47
8.1.2. Data preparation	47
8.1.3. Exploratory data analysis and modeling	48
8.1.4. Results	49
9. 3D mapping options	51
10. list of references.....	52

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of the available proximal sensors and their application for soil measurements	10
Table 2: Descriptive statistics and laboratory method for the analysis of soil properties in the Slovenian case study. The soil types were described as Dystric and Eutric Cambisols on alluvial deposits and metamorphic rocks on row crops.	17
Table 3: Accuracy metrics for digital soil mapping of 3 different parameters using the Slovenian dataset. The analysis incorporates soil proximal sensors data. « AllProx » meaning Gamma+ EMI+VNIR+XRF	21
Table 4: Cost-effectiveness analysis and model performance parameters of estimating soil properties using XRF and VNIR spectra measurements alone or in combination for the dataset in Maribor University’s LTE in Pivola, Slovenia. Dark green formatting indicates the most advantageous method, while light green indicates the least advantageous.	22
<i>Table 5: Descriptive statistics and laboratory method analysis for soil field data. Calcaric Cambisols and Vertic Cambisols on alluvial and lacustrine deposits on row crops</i>	23
Table 6. Accuracy metrics for digital soil mapping for the Italian dataset. The analysis incorporates Sentinel-2 data, with SatProxCov representing combined resources from remote sensing, proximal sensing, and other covariates	26
Table 7: Cost-effectiveness analysis and model performance parameters of estimating soil properties using XRF and VNIR spectra measurements alone or in combination for the dataset in the Fagna LTE experiment in Scarperia, Italy. Dark green formatting indicates the most advantageous method, while light green indicates the least advantageous.	26
Table 8: Ranges of variation of soil properties in the Ikizce municipality, Ankara (Turkey). Soils were described as Haplic Calcisols on moderate-slope high hills on metamorphic rock. The land use is row crops.	28
Table 9: List of ancillary variables (raster layers) used in the modeling process for the spatialization of soil properties in the Turkish study case.	29
Table 10: Model parameters and RI index for the CEC, clay, N, and SOC top and subsoil spatializations using sample-based, PSS covariates, DEM, and Sentinel-2 ancillary data. The modeling method is defined in the “Method” column, where IDW is inverse distance weighted, OK is ordinary kriging, and LinReg_RF and PLSR_RF stand for the modeling method using random forest for variables selection. BS indicates what modeling method for the sample-based group of data represents the baseline from which the RI index (increase in accuracy) is calculated.	34
Table 11: Cost-effectiveness analysis and model performance parameters of estimating soil properties using XRF and VNIR spectra measurements alone or in combination for the dataset in the Ikizce municipality in the Ankara region, Turkey. Dark green formatting indicates the most advantageous method, while light green indicates the least advantageous.	39
Table 12: Overview of the moderately performing models and the selected data layers	44
Table 13: Descriptive statistics of samples’ SOC content (%)	49
Table 14: SOC modeling results (field spectra)	49
Table 15: SOC modeling results (lab spectra).....	51

List of Figures

Figure 1: The synergies of ProbeField with the different internal EJP SOIL projects	11
Figure 2: Decision flowchart for soil survey strategies, modeling activities, and cost-benefit framework calculation.	11

Figure 3: Sampling cost report form for PSS surveys to calculate the cost-benefit framework. 13

Figure 4: A chart showing the variation of the E index (cost-benefit) as the number of samples analyzed increase. 16

Figure 5: The study area is located in the Pivola district, in the Hoče-Slivnica region of Slovenia. The black points represent the sampling locations selected from different management areas. 18

Figure 6: Correlation matrices of the four soil properties in Maribor University’s LTE experiment in Pivola, Slovenia. In this example, only correlations with the PSS covariates are shown. 20

Figure 7: Baselines and best-model-spatializations of CEC, clay, N, and SOC in Maribor University’s LTE field in Pivola, Slovenia. 21

Figure 8: The study area is located in Fagna, within the Florence administrative unit. The black points represent sampling locations selected using a regular gridding. 23

Figure 9: Correlation matrices of the four soil properties in CREA’s LTE in Fagna, Italy. In this example, only correlations with the PSS covariates are shown. 24

Figure 10: Baselines and best-model predictions of CEC, clay, N, and SOC in Fagna, the Fagna LTE field in Scarperia, Italy. 25

Figure 11: Location of the study area in the Ikizce municipality in Ankara, Turkey. Plots cover fifteen hectares of surface in total. Black points represent the sampling locations selected by stratified random sampling using the Copernicus DEM (30 m resolution), and the 24/04/2024 Sentinel-2 image. 27

Figure 12: Spatializations of PSS ancillary variables collected during the survey in the Ikizce municipality’s five fields in the Ankara region, Turkey. DEM is the digital elevation model interpolated using the altitude data extracted from the GPS tracks collected with the EM38-MK2 sensor. Soil temperature (°C) and moisture (%) are the spatializations that resulted from interpolating TDR data at the sampling locations. HCP 0.5 and 1 m are the ECa (dS m⁻¹) spatializations of the signal from receivers (RX) at 0.5 and 1 m away from the transmitter (TX) in the horizontal coplanar configuration of the EM38-MK2 sensor. Counts per second (cps), total count (tc), and the radionuclides are the quantum counting of gamma radiation in Bq Kg⁻¹ of soil in frequency (cps), the total number of quanta at each location (tc) and attributed to each radionuclide spectra (⁴⁰K, ¹³⁷Cs, ²³²Th, and ²³⁸U). 31

Figure 13: Regression matrices for CEC and clay in the topsoil (0-30 cm) and subsoil (30-60 cm) datasets with PSS covariates, DEM, and Sentinel-2 ancillary variables. Colors are assigned based on the Pearson coefficient value. 32

Figure 14: Baselines (charts in the left) for topsoil (upper left) and subsoil (bottom left) datasets, and best model prediction (charts in the right) for topsoil (upper right) and subsoil (bottom right) datasets for CEC in the Ikizce municipality in the Ankara region in Turkey. 35

Figure 15: Baselines (charts in the left) for topsoil (upper left) and subsoil (bottom left) datasets, and best model prediction (charts in the right) for topsoil (upper right) and subsoil (bottom right) datasets for clay in the Ikizce municipality in the Ankara region in Turkey. 36

Figure 16: Baselines (charts in the left) for topsoil (upper left) and subsoil (bottom left) datasets, and best model prediction (charts in the right) for topsoil (upper right) and subsoil (bottom right) datasets for N in the Ikizce municipality in the Ankara region in Turkey. 37

Figure 17: Baselines (charts in the left) for topsoil (upper left) and subsoil (bottom left) datasets, and best model prediction (charts in the right) for topsoil (upper right) and subsoil (bottom right) datasets for SOC in the Ikizce municipality in the Ankara region in Turkey. 38

Figure 18: Calibration and validation sampling locations on the Plassteeg case study site near Wageningen, the Netherlands, consisting of two arable fields. 40

Figure 19: Correlation matrix for Plassteeg field (Netherlands) of several soil properties with the available baselines (S2: Sentinel-2, Sat21: Satellite 2021, Sat20: Satellite 2020, ahn: Dutch elevation

model based on LiDAR, PS: drone Multispectral (proximal), EMI: Electromagnetic Induction (proximal), ga: γ -ray spectrometer (proximal), EC: Electrical Conductivity (proximal), dp: dipole (proximal)) 41

Figure 20: Coefficient of determination (R^2) and Ratio of Performance to Deviation for the models for SOM (2021) based on sample data and baseline data, site Plassteeg, the Netherlands..... 43

Figure 21: Scatterplots for the sample models and the linear models for SOM (2021) (meas, %) against predicted (pred). The predictions were validated using a Leave One Out method..... 44

Figure 22: Accuracy of the models (based on the RPD: Ratio of Performance to Deviation) for the models based on sample data and baseline data, site Plassteeg, the Netherlands (depth 0 till 30 cm) 45

Figure 23: Models for EC based on a) samples only (IDW), b) based on baseline data from all sources (proximal and satellite), site Plassteeg, the Netherlands (depth 0 till 30 cm-sl) using linear regression. 45

Figure 24: Study area in Czech Republic and the sampling points..... 47

Figure 25: SOC content distribution histogram..... 49

Figure 26: Scatter diagrams comparing the observed and predicted SOC values (field spectra) 50

Figure 27: RF-based SOC prediction model’s variable importance plots (field spectra)..... 50

Figure 28: Scatter diagrams comparing the observed and predicted SOC values (lab spectra) 51

Figure 29: RF-based SOC prediction model’s variable importance plots (lab spectra) 51

List of acronyms and abbreviations

- AK – Average Kriging
- CEC – Cation Exchange Capacity
- cLHS – conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling
- CU – Cubist model
- CVI – Chlorophyll Vegetation Index
- DRS – Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy
- E – Cost Effectiveness Index
- DEM – Digital Elevation Model
- DSM – Digital Soil Mapping
- EMI - Electromagnetic induction
- EU – European Union
- EVI – Enhanced Vegetation Index
- FDR – Frequency Domain Reflectometry
- GR – Granger and Ramanathan averaging method
- IDW – Inverse Distance Weighting
- LAI – Leaf Area Index
- LinReg – Linear Regression
- LOOCV – Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation
- MSE – Mean Squared Error
- N – Total Nitrogen

NBR – Normalized Burn Ration
NDVI – Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI – Normalized Difference Water Index
NRMSE – Normalized Root Mean Squared Error
OK – Ordinary Kriging
PCA – Principal Component Analysis
PLSR – Partial Least Square Regression
PSS – Proximal Soil Sensing
pXRF – Portable X-ray Fluorescence
 R^2 – Coefficient of Determination
RF – Random Forest
RI – Relative Increase
RMSE – Root Mean Squared Error
RK – Regression Kriging
RPD - Ratio of Performance to Deviation
RPIQ - Ratio of Performance to Interquartile distance
RS – Remote Sensing
SCS – Spatial Coverage Sampling
SIC – Soil Inorganic Carbon
SOC – Soil Organic Carbon
SNV – Standard Normal Variate
SRS – Stratified Random Sampling
SSL – Soil Spectral Library
TDR – Time Domain Reflectometry
TWI – Topographic Wetness Index
VNIR – Visible and Near-Infrared
UAV – Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
WP – Work Package
XRF – X-ray Fluorescence

1. Introduction

Thanks to technological advances in the 21st century, proximal soil sensing (PSS) is increasingly being adopted as a go-to approach for rapid estimation and high-resolution mapping of soil properties at the local scale. Different practitioners have their own approaches to employing PSS, but a consistent protocol to guide the selection of procedures and to estimate and reduce associated costs is lacking. This protocol is proposed within the Probedfield consortium to help select relevant techniques and determine the associated costs and best data-handling methods for estimating and mapping soil properties. Table 1 gives an overview of the most common PSS techniques and their application fields.

Table 1: Overview of the available proximal sensors and their application for soil measurements

PSS technique	Soil property	Platform	Measurement	Depth
Diffuse reflectance reflectometry (DRS)	SOC, water content, clay minerals, organic matter fractions	Portable, lab, UAV	1D (Point); 2D/3D (maps)	Possibility to acquire data from pits and augers
X-ray fluorescence (XRF)	Elemental composition, clay minerals, heavy metals, nutrients	Portable, lab	1D (Point); 2D/3D (maps)	Possibility to acquire data from pits and augers
Electromagnetic induction (EMI)	Clay content, clay minerals, water content, soil depth, compacted layers, coarse fragments	On-the-go	2D/3D (maps)	Depending on the distance between the transmitter and the receiver. In the market, from 0.3 m to 6 m.
Gamma-ray Spectrometry (γ -ray)	Mineralogy, water content, clay content, clay minerals	On-the-go, UAV	2D/3D (maps)	0-60 cm
Time/Frequency domain reflectometry (TDR/FDR)	Water content	Portable, lab	1D (Point); 2D/3D (maps)	Possibility to acquire data from pits
Ground penetrating radar (GPR)	Soil depth, coarse fragments, compacted layers	On-the-go, UAV	2D/3D (maps)	Up to 10 m restricted by EC

The thought process that went into while devising the protocol has taken into account I) the analysis of costs and accuracy of employing PSS either alone or in combination, II) the evaluation of the accuracy enhancement when advanced mathematical techniques like machine learning are applied to process data and III) the evaluation of the capacity of proximal sensors to produce subsoil mapping of soil properties. The core activities of the final work package of ProbeField WP4 complement well with other EJP Soil internal projects as shown in Figure 1.

The protocol was tested in several case studies to evaluate and compare the performance of various modeling approaches and sensors, individually and in different combinations with other data sources (covariates), for predicting fundamental soil properties (e.g., CEC, clay, SOC, and N), collecting detailed analyses with different sensors and modeling combinations that will help identify critical issues considering a cost-benefit framework for future soil surveys.

Figure 1: The synergies of ProbeField with the different internal EJP SOIL projects

2. A Flow chart about how to decide on the activities

Figure 2 represents a guide through the protocol to help decide the activities to be considered depending on several factors, such as information available and survey purposes.

Figure 2: Decision flowchart for soil survey strategies, modeling activities, and cost-benefit framework calculation.

As we will see in the document, point and on-the-go measurements are evaluated separately, as they represent two distinct phases of the process. Point measurement typically involves the creation of a soil spectral library (SSL) to estimate local soil properties. In this approach, however, point data from TDR, as well as XRF and VNIR spectroscopy, were also used in a georeferenced approach as additional spatial covariates for digital soil mapping (DSM).

The following information should guide the decision process.

I. Collect (existing) information about the area of interest (covariates)

1. Collect covariates such as DEM and Sentinel-2 images.
2. Get the following DEM derivatives: slope, hillshades, TWI, etc.
3. Elaboration from Sentinel-2 images: bare soil mosaic, NBR, soil temperature, NDVI, NDWI, EVI, CVI, LAI, etc.
4. Check if PSS spatial data exists for the area of interest (e.g., EMI and Y-ray sensors).
5. If not, on-the-go PSS surveys need to be preferably performed before planning soil sampling as they would guide the sampling strategy design.

II. Sampling strategy

Before the fieldwork

1. If covariates are available, determine the sampling locations using the information from covariates. Use stratified random sampling (SRS) or conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling (cLHS) to obtain an optimal distribution of sampling points for representative coverage of the geographic and feature spaces. Compare the distributions of points generated with both algorithms by paying attention to the total number of sampling points. Then, decide what distribution better represents the variability of the area.
2. If covariates are unavailable, use spatial coverage sampling (SCS) or a regular grid.

On the field

1. Keep track of the sampling costs (i.e., the time required to complete all the activities) and money if available. Use the sampling cost report form included in this protocol (Figure 3).
2. If possible, collect soil cores at three depths (i.e., 0-30, 30-60, >60 cm until 1 m) using a soil auger.
3. If available, collect the spectra with the spectroradiometer and apply ProbeField's D5.1. best practice protocol to collect soil spectra in the field (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14150972>). We recommend collecting five readings per point. Collect at least five points (replicates) from each soil core from the top to the bottom. Repeat this procedure at each depth. If in-field spectral measurements were taken, the EPO algorithm could be used to correct for soil moisture (Metzger et al., 2024)
4. Collect at least three replicates around each sampling point with TDR/FDR if available.
5. To keep inventory for cost estimates, include all the information recorded in the sampling cost report form (Figure 3) in a linked Excel file for the cost estimation (10.5281/zenodo.14170113). To ensure accuracy estimation, all RMSE values obtained from DSM processing should be included in the dedicated section of the same Excel file. Refer to the data preparation and modeling sections for details.

General information

ID_Site:	Date:	Starting time and total time of the working day:	Fieldworkers:
Country:	Region:	Location:	
Coordinates:		Projection:	Bare soil (percentage):
Land use:	Vegetation cover:	Soil management (tillage, fertilization, mulching, etc):	
Combined (Y/N):	Sensor(s):		
Product type (1D/2D/3D map):	Platform type:	Technique(s):	
Distance to the field:	Personnel costs:	Equipment costs:	

Samples

Study area (ha)	N points:	N samples:	Sampling density:	Samples in depth:	Sampling time (point/sample):
Soil sampling difficulties to report:					

Point measurements

Time of sensor calibration (if any):	
Initial time of the measurement:	Final time of the measurement:
N or lectures (for punctual lectures):	Time taking a lecture:
Measurement difficulties to report:	
Difficulties to report (sensor issues):	

On-the-go measurements

Time of sensor calibration (if any):	
Initial time of the measurement:	Final time of the measurement:
Space between lines:	Measurement difficulties to report:
Difficulties to report (sensor issues):	

Covariates

N of covariates:	Covariate(s) (presence of dataloggers, meteo stations on the field, Drones, RS, etc):
Costs of covariates measurement (indicate what if any):	

Other remarks

Accessibility conditions:
Indicate any other cost:
ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

Figure 3: Sampling cost report form for PSS surveys to calculate the cost-benefit framework.

In the lab

1. Perform the lab analysis (e.g., wet chemistry) of the soil properties of interest.
2. Collect the VNIR spectra from the soil samples after the soil is sieved at 2 mm and air-dried. To keep inventory for cost estimates:

Insert each possible setting for the lab activities into the appropriate sections of the file (10.5281/zenodo.14170113) dedicated to collecting and summarizing cost information. The most relevant information for this purpose includes:

- a) Cost of standard laboratory analysis per sample
- b) Number of samples processed in total and per day
- c) Total cost for point measurement using PSS

III. Data preparation and modeling

1. Harmonization of units, formats, (lab) methods
2. Check for the need to improve the normality of your data by using target and feature engineering.
3. If there are only a few missing values in features, try removing them or doing imputation.
4. Remove zero variance and near-zero variance features.
5. Resample all raster covariates to harmonize them at a consistent finer resolution.
6. Generate a regression matrix using soil properties, PSS, and other covariate data through the spatial modeling script (Digital soil mapping using proximal sensors).
7. The script includes modeling approaches using linear regression (LinReg), partial least squares regression (PLSR), and feature selection based on random forest modeling (RF) for LinReg and PLSR models
8. Other data fusion approaches, such as cubist, random forests, support vector machines, and others, can also be explored. But this is not included in the script as non-linear modelling thrives when datasets with a large number of samples are available, which is often not the case in field-based PSS studies.
9. Perform the validation by applying a leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV).
10. Baseline maps (interpolation) can be created using i) global mean, ii) voronoi polygons, iii) inverse distance weighted, and iv) ordinary kriging for comparison (also included within the script). The best baseline map can be chosen based on LOOCV RMSE. See section V.
11. Report the estimated accuracy in terms of RMSE in the Excel worksheet dedicated to cost information and merge the cost information retrieved from the field and lab.
12. Calculate the cost-benefit formulae using eq 1 and the relative accuracy increase (RI) using eq 2.

IV. Soil survey for validation (testing) purposes

In the case the use of additional independent data for validation is necessary, probability sampling is recommended for validating the PSS-generated soil maps (Brus et al 2011). Stratified simple random sampling is generally a good choice. See if the budget allows for this.

Before the fieldwork

1. Check and follow the instructions in the section “Collect (existing) information about the area of interest” to complete any missing information and select covariates
2. Determine the sampling locations of validation points based on the procedure described above.
3. Perform the fieldwork
4. Validate the existing map.
5. Enter all the new information into (10.5281/zenodo.14170113) “EQ2” Excel Worksheet dedicated to cost information and calculate the gain or loss in the relative accuracy increase (RI) using eq 2.

V. Different spatialization approaches for mapping single soil properties

1. Calculate the average of the soil sampling points.

2. Perform the ordinary kriging of sampling results if distribution of points in space such that a semi-variogram can be modelled, otherwise Inversed Distance Weighing to develop baselines.
3. Apply linear regression of the single soil properties resulting from the sampling with DEM, DEM derivatives, RS, RS derivatives, and PS-covariates to understand the correlation between soil properties and the covariate layers. Apply the best regression models to the covariates to make soil property maps along with uncertainty assessment. Report the accuracy and error metrics.
4. Partial linear regression can be tested in the case of multicollinearity.
5. Random forests or other non linear modelling can be tested if the results from linear modelling are only moderately accurate.
6. If there is spatial variation left, then continue to make a semi-variogram on errors. and apply regression kriging. Report the accuracy and weight of each component of the model.

Note A: Keep track of the accuracy and time needed at each step of the analysis.

VI. Spatial interpolation of multiple soil properties (optional)

1. Novel modelling approaches like multivariate random forests can be employed for simultaneous estimation of soil properties.

VII. Cost-benefits analysis

Cost benefits analysis for point measurement

This section is dedicated to point-based proximal sensors, such as XRF, DRS, and TDR. The accuracy and costs of single and combined detection techniques can be calculated using the "Eq1" Excel worksheet (10.5281/zenodo.14170113). The method proposed by Li et al. (2021) enables a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis compared to standard soil analysis, considering factors such as accuracy, time, and cost. The equation is described as follows:

$$E = \left(\frac{U_r \cdot C_r}{U_s \cdot C_s} \right) \cdot n^{\log_{\alpha_s} \left(\frac{\alpha_s \cdot \beta_s}{\alpha_r \cdot \beta_r} \right)} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq n \leq \alpha \quad \text{Eq 1}$$

Where E is the cost-effectiveness index; n is the number of samples; β is the capacity of data acquisition, otherwise the maximum number of soil samples that can be measured by the method; α is the quantity or capacity of the laboratory to prepare samples for analysis or spectroscopy; U is MSE in %; C is Total cost; r refers to Lab method while s refers to PSS.

The first worksheet provides an explanation with an example, illustrating the sensitivity analysis of E. As shown in Figure 4, when the Mean Squared Error (MSE%) is relatively low (i.e. 10%), the advantage in terms of E increases more rapidly as the number of samples grows.

The detailed data entry in the Eq1 worksheet, as taken from the protocol, is structured as follows:

- i) Specify the settings for duration and working efficiency, as well as the maximum capacity for preparing samples for analysis
- ii) Specify the laboratory method and costs for each parameter, the point measurement sensors used, their cost prices with applied depreciation values.
- iii). Specify the time required for calibration, and the measurements taken with the instrument and Lab method.
- iv) Enter the total number of samples processed, the average parameter value, and the RMSE or MSE derived from spectroscopic modeling.
- v) The methods, costs, and timing of soil survey and sampling.
- vi) Obtaining the overall E-index.

The idea is to repeat the calculation for each parameter across all experiments and configurations, such as VNIR, XRF, or their data fusion. All E values are greater than 0, indicating that each method is still advantageous compared to standard laboratory analysis for the sample size considered.

Figure 4: A chart showing the variation of the E index (cost-benefit) as the number of samples analyzed increase.

The objective of this section was to determine whether integrating measurements from pXRF and Vis-NIR sensors improved the accuracy of soil parameter predictions compared to traditional laboratory analytical methods. This dataset, available at [10.5281/zenodo.14104497](https://zenodo.org/record/14104497), was processed to obtain a cost-benefit analysis using the file available at [10.5281/zenodo.14170113](https://zenodo.org/record/14170113).

The default settings required to solve Eq. 2 and applied in the case studies described below are as follows:

The cost of a complete set of standard laboratory analyses was 65 euros per sample. This total is divided based on the costs of individual analyses. For instance, the CEC measurement is estimated at EUR 15 per sample with a 1-day turnaround, while SOC and Nitrogen measurements cost EUR 4.5, and soil texture analysis costs EUR 5 per sample. Other important metrics include measurement times: approximately 2 minutes per sample for Vis-NIR and 3 minutes per sample for XRF. From these times, we can estimate the daily processing capacity: about 210 soil samples per day for Vis-NIR, 140 samples for pXRF, or around 85 samples for a day if both Vis-NIR and pXRF are used simultaneously. Of course, these initial parameters can be adjusted by the user to suit their specific case study.

Cost benefits for integrating point measurement with on-the-go sensors

This section considers all information according to the protocol to perform a cost-benefit analysis of the combined sensor approach, which involves using moving sensors, point measurement sensors, and morphometric or remote sensing covariates. This activity includes a spatial modeling script (“Digital Soil Mapping Using Proximal Sensors”) that progressively selects predictors and models, resulting in DSMs as the outcome. The file [10.5281/zenodo.14170113](https://zenodo.org/record/14170113) provides an explanation after the 'readme' section, while the EQ2 worksheet is designed for data entry, with each cell specifically described. The cost calculation is based on a simple summation, while accuracy is evaluated by the progressive and relative increase in accuracy in % (RI) as the gain in RMSE according to eq 2

$$RI(\%) = \frac{((RMSE(sample-based\ int.) - (RMSE(PSS)))}{(RMSE(PSS))} * 100$$

Eq 2

The detailed data entry in the Eq 2 worksheet, as taken from the protocol, is structured as follows:

- ii) The first info section provides a general description of the site, the experimental settings (i.e. the sampling method), and the total time required for modeling, validation, calibration, and map generation ii) Specify the on-the-go sensors used, the cost prices with an applied depreciation value, the time required for calibration, and the measurements taken with the instrument. iii) Specify the point measurement sensors used, following the same specifications

as in (ii). iv) The types of covariates used and the time required to elaborate them. v) The methods, costs, and timing of soil survey and sampling. vi) The costs of laboratory analysis, split by individual properties. vii) The results include, on one hand, the total cost € per hectare (Ha) for all processes leading up to the soil map, and on the other hand, the model type, accuracy values, and RI index for each individual parameter.

Simple interpolation methods, such as Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) and Ordinary Kriging (OK), serve as the baseline.

3. Slovenian case study: management-based sampling

3.1. Site description

Four fields were selected in three locations to carry on the sampling campaign in Slovenia. All sites were long-term experiments that belong to different institutions: i) a corn arable crop LTE (Ljubljana University) of one ha surface area where several fertilization treatments were ongoing; ii) a barley arable crop LTE with two fields (one ha approximately each) at the Moskanjci Farm in the Podravje region, where different degrees of tillage and no-tillage treatments were being applied; and iii) a meadow LTE of 0.3 ha surface area (Maribor University) located in the Pivola district within the Podravje region, where different mowing treatments were ongoing. In the Moskanjci LTE experiment, the two fields were in a flat area with Dystric Cambisols developing on alluvial deposits, located explicitly at 46.408°N, 15.996°E (bottom left) and 46.41°N, 16.002°E (upper right). The Ljubljana University's LTE field is located on Eutric Gleysols developing on Pleistocene clays, located at 46.5°N, 15.63°E (centroid). The final location in Pivola featured a flat, mowed meadow with Dystric Cambisols developing on metamorphic rocks, also centered at 46.5°N, 15.63°E. The weather during scanning was sunny, with soil moisture averaging 30% and an average soil temperature of 26°C.

3.2. Proximal soil sensing data and experimental design

Sampling locations were distributed attending to the treatments of each LTE. The resulting dataset consisted of 22 sampling locations where 0-30, 30-60, and 60-90 cm depth samples were collected, when possible, for a total of 65 samples. Further details on the areas and treatments are in the D3.2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14150972>). Due to logistic reasons, this case study will be focused only on mapping the topsoil properties for Maribor University's LTE field (Figure 5). This experimental setup consisted of several mowing treatments of a meadow. Eight locations were sampled at three depths (Figure 5). Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the study area.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics and laboratory method for the analysis of soil properties in the Slovenian case study. The soil types were described as Dystric and Eutric Cambisols on alluvial deposits and metamorphic rocks on row crops.

Maribor, Ljubljana, and Pivola, Slovenia				
Soil variable	Units	Min	Mean	Max
Carbonates	%	0	1	4.4
CEC	meq 100 g ⁻¹	11.4	17.6	21.8
EC 1:5	dS m ⁻¹	0.03	0.08	0.19
Ex_K	meq 100 g ⁻¹	0.05	0.17	0.81
N	g Kg ⁻¹	0.9	1.95	3.5
P	mg Kg ⁻¹	1	15	89
pH H ₂ O	-	5	7	8.3
Sand	%	7	26	52
Silt	%	17	47	63
Clay	%	16	27	38
SOC	%	0.14	1.18	2.59

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020

research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 862695, and from Tillämpningsklivet Precisionsodling RUN 2021–00020 Region Västra Götaland

Figure 5: The study area is located in the Pivola district, in the Hoče-Slivnica region of Slovenia. The black points represent the sampling locations selected from different management areas.

In this example, four PSS sensors were used during the survey, and later, the lecture of the other two sensors were assessed to soil samples under the laboratory conditions to the air-dried and sieved soil samples. 'The Mole' γ -ray spectroradiometer (Soil Company, Netherlands), the EM38-MK2 electromagnetic induction sensor (Geonics Ltd., Ontario, Canada), a FieldScout TDR 300, and the Spectral Evolution SR-6500 spectroradiometer were used for in-situ data collection. Both the on-the-go sensors (i.e., the γ -ray spectroradiometer and the EM38-MK2) collected data on the walk, keeping an interline distance of approximately 10 m. The in-field spectra acquisition was conducted for topsoil, while the spectra for subsoil samples were collected using a ASD FieldSpec Pro 3. For spectra acquisition, the soil surface was treated using the D5.1 In-field spectra data collection protocol (Stenberg et. al. 2024). The reference base spectra of the Lucky Bay sands were used to make comparable spectral datasets from the two sensors. Five replicates were acquired from both topsoil and subsoil measurements. In-field spectra data were corrected using the EPO algorithm to account for soil moisture, whereas soil samples were dried and sieved to <2 mm to prepare samples for spectra collection in the laboratory. A soil subsample (5 g) was extracted from each sample to be sent to the CSIC headquarters in Seville for the x-ray fluorescence data acquisition with a Niton XL3t 950s GOLDD analyzer.

3.3. Data preparation

The horizontal coplanar of the 0.5 m and 1 m receivers of the EM38-MK2 were selected to produce the EC_a maps of the field. The 0.5 and 1 m datasets were cleaned of outliers and merged to be then spatialized using ordinary kriging. The same procedure was applied to γ -ray spectra: the GAMMAN software allowed the identification of outliers and the extraction of radionuclides spectra (i.e., ^{40}K , ^{137}Cs , ^{232}Th , and ^{238}U). In addition, the counts per second (cps) and total count (tc) datasets were extracted. Subsequently, γ -ray data were spatialized using ordinary kriging for a total of six layers. The TDR sensor furnishes four data by lecture (i.e., temperature, a moisture lecture calibrated for soils with high clay content, a standard soil moisture lecture, and electrical conductivity). VNIR spectra data were treated as described in the D5.1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14150972>): 1) the raw spectra were reduced in the range between 400 and 2450 to remove the spectrum tails; 2) the spline interpolation was applied to the tailored spectra; 3) Savitzky-Golay smoothing filter using a second polynomial order and a window of 11 nm was applied; 4) spectral data were detrended by applying a SNV transformation; 5) the spectral alignment was obtained applying a different correction factor for each spectroradiometer that takes the Lucky Bay sands as an internal soil standard. XRF data were transformed using the SNV transformation to detrend the spectral data. This spectral data pretreatment was followed by the calculation of PCs aiming to spatialize by OK interpolation the components and use them as additional covariates in Digital Soil Mapping of soil properties.

3.4. Modeling of Point Measurements Using VNIR and XRF

The prediction method chosen for estimating soil parameters from Vis-NIR and XRF spectra was Cubist, a rule-based regression approach. To facilitate the integration of the Vis-NIR and pXRF spectra, we used the average model predictions obtained through bootstrapping in the data fusion method proposed by Granger and Ramanathan (1984). This method applies a multiple linear regression to the average model predictions, assigning weights to the predictors, which are then used in Eq. 3 to predict individual soil parameters

$$Y = W_0 + (W_{\text{vnir}} * X_{\text{vnir}}) + (W_{\text{xrf}} * X_{\text{xrf}}) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where Y is the soil parameter value predicted through model averaging, W₀ is the y-intercept derived from the linear model, W_{vnir} and X_{vnir} are the respective VNIR weighting and predictions, and W_{xrf} and X_{xrf} are the respective weighting and predictions for XRF.

3.5. Exploratory data analysis and modeling

The baselines were established by comparing the modeling parameters of three methods: i) Global Mean, ii) inverse distance weighted, and iii) ordinary kriging. We considered as the baseline of each soil property the lowest RMSE value in each case. In contrast, the accuracy of the modeling process was evaluated by comparing whether there was an increase or decrease of the RMSE and R² to the respective baseline. Such variation was quantified using the RI index described in the cost-benefit analysis section above in this document.

Correlation matrices for N, SOC, clay, and CEC with variables in the topsoil dataset were calculated to establish a sorting of variables and check for collinearity. Variables were considered collinear when Pearson's coefficient > 0.5.

The modeling methods tested were i) linear regressions (LinReg), and ii) partial least-square regressions (PLSR). Then, a non-linear modeling process was applied to select the most influential variables using random forest (RF). Subsequently, those variables were utilized to compare the variation in the accuracy of spatializations using LinReg and PLSR. Then, the exploration process of the four soil properties data was tested as follows in the topsoil and subsoil datasets:

1. with the ancillary variables of the on-the-go sensors were tested separately;
2. with the ancillary variables created using the point measurements of portable sensors (TDR, ASD Fieldspec, and XRF) altogether.
3. with the DEM and Sentinel-2 covariates only (topsoil), and with the DEM covariates only (subsoil);
4. with on-the-go sensors ancillary variables, DEM, and Sentinel-2 covariates for the topsoil dataset, and with on-the-go sensors ancillary variables and DEM for the subsoil dataset;
5. with all the covariates together.

For this example in the site Pivola, 9 topsoil samples were collected and analyzed over a 0.3 ha area. The soil properties considered are SOC, clay, CEC, and N. The use of DEM or Sentinel-2 imagery was excluded for this example, only PSS covariates were used in the modeling process.

Figure 6: Correlation matrices of the four soil properties in Maribor University's LTE experiment in Pivola, Slovenia. In this example, only correlations with the PSS covariates are shown.

3.6. Result: in-field multi-sensor system and accuracy variation

The model with the smallest RMSE and a high RI is based on a combination of all PSS sensors on PLSR modeling with Random Forest feature selection. In this case, using EMI and a linear model for SOC and clay may be more convenient. For predicting SOC, the principal component mapping of VNIR+XRF data proved beneficial.

Figure 7: Baselines and best-model-spatializations of CEC, clay, N, and SOC in Maribor University's LTE field in Pivola, Slovenia.

Pivola		SOC			N			clay			CEC		
Method	Data	R ²	RMSE	RI %	R ²	RMSE	RI %	R ²	RMSE	RI %	R ²	RMSE	RI %
Gmean	Samples	1.00	0.58		1.00	1.12		1.00	4.99		1.00	1.56	
IDW	Samples	0.30	0.44	BS	0.62	0.72		0.28	3.91	BS	0.32	1.24	
OK	Samples	0.45	0.38		0.79	0.51	BS	0.00	4.39		0.45	1.05	BS
LinReg	EMI	0.59	0.33	15	0.52	0.70	-27	0.62	2.81	39	0.28	1.25	-16
LinReg	VNIR-XRF	0.66	0.30	26	0.51	0.73	-31	0.06	5.28	-26	0.12	1.53	-31
LinReg	Gamma	0.06	0.91	-58	0.35	0.85	-40	0.01	6.44	-39	0.01	2.31	-55
PLSR	EMI	0.78	0.24	59	0.60	0.72	-29	0.81	1.90	105	0.58	0.88	19
PLSR	AllProx	0.89	0.17	126	0.87	0.47	8	0.92	1.27	208	0.93	0.37	184
LinReg_RF	AllProx	0.30	1.01	-62	0.70	0.49	4	0.77	2.12	85	0.68	0.79	32
PLSR_RF	AllProx	0.90	0.16	139	0.90	0.35	46	0.93	1.18	231	0.91	0.41	158

Table 3: Accuracy metrics for digital soil mapping of 3 different parameters using the Slovenian dataset. The analysis incorporates soil proximal sensors data. « AllProx » meaning Gamma+ EMI+VNIR+XRF

3.7. Result: estimation of properties with VNIR and XRF, and cost-benefit index application

In terms of E value, the VNIR technique was found to be more convenient for most standard soil analyses, while XRF and data fusion were more effective for CEC. In terms of accuracy alone, the data fusion approach significantly improved results for SOC and N. Although the combined approach often achieves better measurement accuracy, the lower E-index indicates that it may be less cost-effective due to the higher work effort required. See Table 4. Accuracy metrics and the E-index are provided for SOC, N, Clay, and CEC.

Slovenia Pivola, Maribor, spectroscopy model performance and cost-effectiveness index						
Property	Sensor	R ²	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	E index
SOC	VNIR	0.87	0.26	2.82	4.24	0.3
SOC	XRF	0.84	0.29	2.52	3.79	0.2
SOC	VNIR+XRF	0.91	0.21	3.48	2.83	0.2
N	VNIR	0.80	0.33	2.26	2.91	0.2
N	XRF	0.84	0.29	2.52	3.23	0.2
N	VNIR+XRF	0.92	0.19	3.81	1.8	0.2
clay	VNIR	0.72	2.66	1.92	2.92	2.0
clay	XRF	0.64	3.03	1.68	2.56	1.0
clay	VNIR+XRF	0.75	2.44	2.08	1.49	1.2
CEC	VNIR	0.81	1.14	2.33	1.41	4.3
CEC	XRF	0.94	0.65	4.07	2.46	7.9
CEC	VNIR+XRF	0.93	0.64	4.1	1.24	4.3

Table 4: Cost-effectiveness analysis and model performance parameters of estimating soil properties using XRF and VNIR spectra measurements alone or in combination for the dataset in Maribor University's LTE in Pivola, Slovenia. Dark green formatting indicates the most advantageous method, while light green indicates the least advantageous.

4. Italian case study: regular grid sampling

4.1. Site description

The study was conducted at the Fagna Farm of the CREA Institute in Italy, located at 43.9836°N, 11.347°E (centroid), with an altitude of 260 meters. The environment comprises row crops on Calcaric Cambisols evolved on recent Holocene fluvial sediments and Vertic Cambisol evolved on Pleistocene lacustrine silty-clay sediments. Descriptive statistics for the soil are provided in Table 5. The site, covering 6 hectares and divided into 3 parcels, consists of about 90% bare soil. Sampling locations were distributed by applying the regular grid strategy. The survey took 6 hours to complete, with 3 operators collecting data from 39 sites and gathering a total of 60 samples. The weather at the time of scanning was sunny, with soil moisture averaging 25%, average soil surface temperature was 9°C. Four sensors were tested simultaneously on the field: i) an EM38-MK2 electromagnetic induction sensor (Geonics Limited, Canada), ii) a γ -ray "The Mole" spectroradiometer (The Soil Company, the Netherlands), iii) an ASD Fieldspec 3 (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., UK), and iv) a time-domain reflectometer (TDR) FieldScout 150 (Spectrum Technologies, UK). The sampling procedure was carried on as follows: one soil sample was collected at each location from the topsoil (0–30 cm), and an additional subsoil sample (30–60 cm) was collected only in the LTE parcel using an auger. Simultaneously, three TDR lectures (replicates) on soil moisture and temperature were collected at three points around the auger hole. An additional 15 soil data points, inferred spectroscopically in situ, were collected from locations other than the sampling points. Simultaneously, the survey with the EM38-MK2 and the γ -ray spectroradiometer was performed by walking, keeping an interline distance of approximately 10

meters. Samples were air-dried and conserved in a plastic bag. Then, they were taken to the CREA’s headquarters in Florence, where they were sieved at 2 mm. Five grams of each soil sample was taken apart and sent to the CSIC headquarters in Seville, Spain, to obtain the lecture with the XRF sensor, whereas a certified external laboratory from the Liguria Region, Italy, performed the soil analyses of topsoil and subsoil samples. The soil properties determined were SOC, clay, sand, silt, N, P, CEC, EC, exchangeable bases, pH, active and total carbonates.

Fagna, Italy				
Soil variable	Units	Min	Mean	Max
Carbonates	%	0.4	6.2	25.7
CEC	meq 100 g ⁻¹	12.5	17.5	30.4
EC 1:5	dS m ⁻¹	0.09	0.13	0.16
Ex_K	meq 100 g ⁻¹	0.3	0.45	0.68
N	g Kg ⁻¹	1.19	1.55	2.16
P	mg Kg ⁻¹	1	18	47
pH H ₂ O	-	7.7	8.2	8.4
Sand	%	2	37	62
Silt	%	23	34	46
Clay	%	15	29	63
SOC	%	0.46	0.9	1.36

Table 5: Descriptive statistics and laboratory method analysis for soil field data. Calcaric Cambisols and Vertic Cambisols on alluvial and lacustrine deposits on row crops

Figure 8: The study area is located in Fagna, within the Florence administrative unit. The black points represent sampling locations selected using a regular gridding.

4.2. Exploratory data analysis and modeling

DSM of CEC, clay, N and SOC properties was tested in site Fagna. Ancillary variables like DEM or Sentinel-2 images were used in this activity. The selected Sentinel-2 image presented the highest bare soil percent and lowest cloud cover percent. The dependence between the ancillary variables in the topsoil is shown in the correlation matrix for the four soil properties used in this example (Fig. 6). Typically, autocorrelation exists between the covariates from the same sensor (e.g., γ -ray covariates, EMI covariates, Sentinel-2 bands), and some soil properties.

For point measurements, the Cubist method was chosen to estimate soil parameters from individual Vis-NIR and XRF spectra. To combine the Vis-NIR and pXRF spectra, we applied the Granger and Ramanathan average model. Check the modeling procedure in section 3.5 of this document.

Figure 9: Correlation matrices of the four soil properties in CREA’s LTE in Fagna, Italy. In this example, only correlations with the PSS covariates are shown.

4.3. Results: in-field multi-sensor system and accuracy variation

SOC shows weak correlations with all variables, while clay and CEC exhibit moderate to strong correlations with the auxiliary variables. The combination of all PSS sensors, combined with Random Forest feature selection in PLSR modeling, produces the best results. The multiple linear regression model using all auxiliary variables is effective, except for SOC. In a linear model setting, the Sentinel-2 bare soil image outperforms the use of γ -ray and EMI proximal sensors. In this context, using spatialized PCA of XRF and NIR may be a more efficient approach.

Figure 10: Baselines and best-model predictions of CEC, clay, N, and SOC in Fagna, the Fagna LTE field in Scarperia, Italy.

Fagna		SOC			N			Clay			CEC		
Method	Data	R ²	RMSE	RI%	R ²	RMSE	RI%	R ²	RMSE	RI%	R ²	RMSE	RI%
Gmean	Samples	1.00	0.181		1.00	0.25		1.00	16.3		1.00	5.8	
IDW	Samples	0.10	0.175		0.36	0.20		0.90	5.1	BS	0.88	1.9	BS
OK	Samples	0.07	0.172	BS	0.38	0.19	BS	0.84	9.3		0.86	2.1	
LinReg	S2-dem	0.06	0.178	-3.4	0.28	0.21	-8.6	0.87	5.6	-9.9	0.89	1.9	2.7
LinReg	EMI	0.05	0.181	-5.2	0.23	0.22	-10.5	0.81	6.9	-25.7	0.74	2.9	-31.9
LinReg	VNIR-XRF-TDR	0.09	0.171	0.5	0.17	0.23	-13.9	0.91	4.9	4.7	0.89	1.8	6.7
LinReg	Gamma	0.05	0.181	-5.2	0.39	0.19	0.2	0.80	7.0	-27.7	0.71	3.0	-35.4
LinReg	SatProxCov	0.09	0.177	-2.8	0.52	0.17	12.2	0.92	4.4	15.9	0.92	1.6	18.6
PLSR	S2-dem	0.08	0.169	1.8	0.08	0.24	-17.7	0.72	8.3	-39.0	0.81	2.4	-20.3
PLSR	EMI	0.04	0.173	-0.6	0.20	0.22	-11.7	0.82	6.6	-23.4	0.84	2.2	-12.3
PLSR	VNIR-XRF-TDR	0.07	0.170	1.1	0.24	0.21	-9.6	0.92	4.6	11.6	0.90	1.7	11.8
PLSR	Gamma	0.03	0.173	-1.0	0.50	0.17	11.3	0.78	7.4	-31.0	0.66	3.3	-41.0
LinReg_RF	SatProxCov	0.06	0.173	-0.8	0.52	0.17	13.7	0.91	4.9	4.7	0.88	2.0	-0.6

PLSR_RF	SatProxCov	0.14	0.163	5.2	0.62	0.15	28.9	0.92	4.5	14.0	0.89	1.9	4.5
---------	------------	------	-------	-----	------	------	------	------	-----	------	------	-----	-----

Table 6. Accuracy metrics for digital soil mapping for the Italian dataset. The analysis incorporates Sentinel-2 data, with SatProxCov representing combined resources from remote sensing, proximal sensing, and other covariates

4.4. Result: estimation of properties with VNIR and XRF, and cost-benefit index application

In terms of E value, the VNIR technique was found to be more effective for all the parameters considered. However, good responses were also obtained from XRF for Clay and CEC. Although the combined approach achieves better measurement accuracy, the lower E index might indicate a disproportionate allocation of resources (Table 7).

Italy, Fagna, spectroscopy model performance and cost-effectiveness index						
Property	Sensor	R ²	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	E_index
SOC	VNIR	0.50	0.13	1.43	2.13	1.2
SOC	XRF	0.18	0.17	1.11	1.66	0.4
SOC	VNIR+XRF	0.51	0.12	1.45	1.01	0.4
N	VNIR	0.87	0.09	2.8	3.81	2.2
N	XRF	0.22	0.22	1.15	1.56	0.5
N	VNIR+XRF	0.88	0.085	3.01	2.57	0.7
clay	VNIR	0.97	2.38	5.96	5.43	2.4
clay	XRF	0.97	2.55	5.55	5.06	1.2
clay	VNIR+XRF	0.97	2.24	6.29	1.10	1.3
CEC	VNIR	0.95	1.07	4.73	5.89	3.9
CEC	XRF	0.96	1.07	4.76	5.93	2.3
CEC	VNIR+XRF	0.96	0.93	5.44	4.99	1.7

Table 7: Cost-effectiveness analysis and model performance parameters of estimating soil properties using XRF and VNIR spectra measurements alone or in combination for the dataset in the Fagna LTE experiment in Scarperia, Italy. Dark green formatting indicates the most advantageous method, while light green indicates the least advantageous.

5. Turkish case study: stratified random sampling

5.1. Site description

The study was conducted in the İkişce Municipality, in Ankara (Figure 10), at the coordinates 39.591°N, 32.683°E (bottom left), and 39.596°N, 32.700°E (upper right). The targeted area is a farm located at 1060 m altitude placed at the disposal of the General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies (TAGEM, acronym in Turkish) by the landowners. It consisted of five fields for approximately fifteen hectares. The surrounding environment comprises row crops on gently to moderately sloping hills, with Calcisols developing on various metamorphic rock types. Descriptive statistics for the soil are provided in Table 8. The five fields were 80% bare soil at the time of the survey.

Figure 11: Location of the study area in the İkişce municipality in Ankara, Turkey. Plots cover fifteen hectares of surface in total. Black points represent the sampling locations selected by stratified random sampling using the Copernicus DEM (30 m resolution), and the 24/04/2024 Sentinel-2 image.

To represent the variability of the area and distribute sampling locations, the stratified random sampling (SRS) algorithm was applied using the digital elevation model and derivatives (es. slope, hillshades) and indexes calculated on Sentinel-2 imagery from April 2024 (es. normalized burn ratio, NBR) as stratification layers. Due to the lack of prior knowledge about the area and logistic and timing limitations, using on-the-go PSS spatial data in the sampling design stage was not possible. However, a PSS survey using on-the-go EM38-MK2 and a γ -ray spectroradiometer was carried out, aiming to use them during the data modeling process. The distribution of sampling locations process threw out forty-one points as a spatially optimal representative design.

Four sensors were tested simultaneously on the field: i) an EM38-MK2 electromagnetic induction sensor (Geonics Limited, Canada), ii) a γ -ray “The Mole” spectroradiometer (The Soil Company, the Netherlands), iii) an ASD Fieldspec 3 (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., UK), and iv) a time-domain reflectometer (TDR) FieldScout 150 (Spectrum Technologies, UK). The sampling procedure was performed as follows: two soil samples were collected at each location (i.e., topsoil 0-30 cm and subsoil 30-60 cm) using an auger. Simultaneously, three TDR lectures (replicates) on soil moisture and temperature were collected at three points around the auger hole. In addition, three lectures were collected along the auger core at the two depths in all locations. In parallel, the survey with the EM38-MK2 and the γ -ray spectroradiometer was performed by walking, keeping an interline distance of approximately 20 meters. Five operators performed the whole survey within eight hours. The weather was stable and cloudy; however, heavy rain occurred the day before and after the sampling. Average soil moisture and temperature were 35% and 15.5 °C, respectively. Samples were air-dried and conserved in a plastic bag. Then, they were taken to the CREA’s headquarters in Florence, where they were sieved at 2 mm. Five grams of each soil sample was taken apart and sent to the CSIC headquarters in Seville, Spain, to obtain the lecture with the XRF sensor, whereas a certified external laboratory from the Liguria Region, Italy, performed the soil analyses on both topsoil and subsoil samples. The soil properties determined were SOC, clay, sand, silt, N, P, CEC, EC, exchangeable bases, pH, active and total carbonates. Only results for N, SOC, clay, and CEC will be shown in this example.

İkizce, Turkey				
Soil variable	Units	Min	Mean	Max
Carbonates	%	16.1	25	38.5
CEC	meq 100 g ⁻¹	23.4	29.8	37.2
Clay	%	35	53	66
EC 1:5	dS m ⁻¹	0.12	0.16	0.48
Ex_K	meq 100 g ⁻¹	0.25	0.57	1.18
N	g Kg ⁻¹	0.72	1.35	1.81
P	mg Kg ⁻¹	2	7.4	45
pH H₂O	-	8.2	8.5	9
Sand	%	8	25	43
Silt	%	14	22	35
SOC	%	0.19	0.85	1.21

Table 8: Ranges of variation of soil properties in the İkizce municipality, Ankara (Turkey). Soils were described as Haplic Calcisols on moderate-slope high hills on metamorphic rock. The land use is row crops.

Specific treatment was applied to each dataset collected from each sensor. For this example, the horizontal coplanar of the 0.5 m and 1 m receivers of the EM38-MK2 were selected to produce the EC_a maps of the five plots. Each plot’s 0.5 and 1 m datasets were cleaned of outliers and merged to be then spatialized using ordinary kriging. The same procedure was applied to each plot’s γ -ray spectra: the GAMMAN software allowed the identification of outliers and the extraction of radionuclides spectra (i.e., ⁴⁰K, ¹³⁷Cs, ²³²Th, and ²³⁸U). In addition, the counts per second (cps) and total count (tc) datasets were extracted for each plot. Subsequently, they were merged and spatialized using ordinary kriging for a total of six layers. The TDR sensor furnishes four data per reading (i.e., temperature, a moisture lecture calibrated for soils with high clay content, a standard soil moisture reading, and electrical conductivity). The three replicates of the TDR were averaged, and temperature and high clay content soil moisture lectures were spatialized using ordinary kriging. The soil spectra collected with ASD Fieldspec were treated as in section 3.3 of this document. Then, an analysis of principal components (PCA) was used to summarize the spectra of top and subsoil samples. Subsequently, the first two components were spatialized using ordinary kriging. The same procedure was applied to the XRF spectra.

In addition, a fine-resolution DEM was created by interpolating the altitude data collected from the GPS tracks of the on-the-go PSS survey. Bands from the 9th of June Sentinel-2 image were used as

ancillary variables, too. The whole set of covariates used in this example is shown in Table 9. All of them were resampled to the same pixel dimension (2.3 m).

Ikizce, Turkey		
Sensor	Covariate	Applicability
γ-ray spectroradiometer	tc	0-30
	cps	0-30
	40K	0-30
	137Cs	0-30
	232Th	0-30
	238U	0-30
EM38-MK2	HPC 0.5 m	0-50
	HPC 1 m	0-100
	Fine resolution DEM	Topsoil
ASD Fieldspec	PC1-topsoil	0-30
	PC2-topsoil	0-30
	PC1-subsoil	30-60
	PC2-subsoil	30-60
XRF	PC1-topsoil	0-30
	PC1-subsoil	30-60
TDR	Temperature	Topsoil
	Moisture	Topsoil
Sentinel-2 (09/06/2024)	S2-B01	Topsoil
	S2-B02	Topsoil
	S2-B03	Topsoil
	S2-B04	Topsoil
	S2-B05	Topsoil
	S2-B06	Topsoil
	S2-B07	Topsoil
	S2-B08	Topsoil
	S2-B08A	Topsoil
	S2-B10	Topsoil
	S2-B11	Topsoil
	S2-B12	Topsoil

Table 9: List of ancillary variables (raster layers) used in the modeling process for the spatialization of soil properties in the Turkish study case.

5.2. Exploratory data analysis and modeling

The baselines were established by comparing the modeling parameters of four methods: i) Global Mean, ii) Voronoi polygons, iii) inverse distance weighted, and iv) ordinary kriging. We considered as the baseline of each soil property the lowest RMSE value in each case. In contrast, the accuracy of the modeling process was evaluated by comparing whether there was an increase or decrease of the RMSE and R^2 to the respective baseline. Such variation was quantified using the RI index defined in the cost-benefit analysis section of this document.

Correlation matrices for N, SOC, clay, and CEC with variables in top- and sub-soil datasets were calculated to establish a sorting of variables and check for collinearity. Variables were considered collinear when Pearson's coefficient > 0.5 .

The linear modeling methods tested were i) linear regressions (LinReg), and ii) partial least-square regressions (PLSR). Then, a non-linear modeling process was applied to select the most influential variables using random forest (RF). Subsequently, those variables were utilized to compare the variation in the accuracy of spatializations using LinReg and PLSR. Then, the exploration process of the four soil properties data was tested as follows in the topsoil and subsoil datasets:

1. with the ancillary variables of the on-the-go sensors were tested separately;

2. with the ancillary variables created using the point measurements of portable sensors (TDR, ASD Fieldspec, and XRF) altogether;
3. with the DEM and Sentinel-2 covariates only (topsoil), and with the DEM covariates only (subsoil);
4. with on-the-go sensors ancillary variables, DEM, and Sentinel-2 covariates for the topsoil dataset, and with on-the-go sensors ancillary variables and DEM for the subsoil dataset;
5. with all the covariates together.

On the other hand, the cubist model was selected to estimate the four soil properties with PSS point measurements (i.e., VNIR and XRF techniques independently and then in combination). The spectra collected with both techniques were combined using the Granger and Ramanathan average model.

Figure 12: Spatializations of PSS ancillary variables collected during the survey in the Ikizce municipality's five fields in the Ankara region, Turkey. DEM is the digital elevation model interpolated using the altitude data extracted from the GPS tracks collected with the EM38-MK2 sensor. Soil temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and moisture (%) are the spatializations that resulted from interpolating TDR data at the sampling locations. HCP 0.5 and 1 m are the ECa (dS m^{-1}) spatializations of the signal from receivers (RX) at 0.5 and 1 m away from the transmitter (TX) in the horizontal coplanar configuration of the EM38-MK2 sensor. Counts per second (cps), total count (tc), and the radionuclides are the quantum counting of gamma radiation in Bq Kg^{-1} of soil in frequency (cps), the total number of quanta at each location (tc) and attributed to each radionuclide spectra (^{40}K , ^{137}Cs , ^{232}Th , and ^{238}U).

5.3. Results: in-field multi-sensor system and accuracy variation

The dependence between the ancillary variables in the topsoil and subsoil datasets is shown in the correlation matrices for the four soil properties used in this example (Figures 12 and 13). Typically, autocorrelation exists between the covariates from the same sensor (e.g., γ -ray covariates, EMI covariates, Sentinel-2 bands), and some soil properties.

Figure 13: Regression matrices for CEC and clay in the topsoil (0-30 cm) and subsoil (30-60 cm) datasets with PSS covariates, DEM, and Sentinel-2 ancillary variables. Colors are assigned based on the Pearson coefficient value.

The strongest correlations with the proximal and sentinel bands were selected to perform the linear regression models and PLSRs for CEC, clay, N, and SOC in the 0-30 and 30-60 cm depth. Akaike’s Information Criterion index selected the best model for each case automatically.

Figure 13: Regression matrices for N and SOC in the topsoil (0-30 cm) and subsoil (30-60 cm) datasets with PSS and DEM covariates. Colors are assigned based on the Pearson coefficient value.

The baseline for each soil property and depth was defined using sample-based interpolations. Any increase (or decrease) in the accuracy of spatializations (RMSE) using the ancillary variables was accounted for using the RI index. Table 10 shows all the modeling strategies with the associated model parameters (R^2 and RMSE), as well as the RI that represents the variation in accuracy with respect to the baseline (BS) for each soil property and depth.

Turkey			CEC			Clay			N			SOC		
Method	Data	Layer	R ²	RMSE	RI%	R ²	RMSE	RI%	R ²	RMSE	RI%	R ²	RMSE	RI%
Global mean	Samples	Topsoil	1.000	2.878		1.000	5.591		1.000	0.219		1.000	0.154	
Global mean	Samples	Subsoil	1.000	3.075		1.000	6.654		1.000	0.234		1.000	0.226	
Voronoi polygons	Samples	Topsoil	0.195	2.858		0.001	8.206		0.011	0.298		0.009	0.217	
Voronoi polygons	Samples	Subsoil	0.242	3.148		0.052	8.282		0.145	0.266		0.001	0.326	
IDW	Samples	Topsoil	0.197	2.534	BS	0.000	6.232		0.043	0.246		0.017	0.170	
IDW	Samples	Subsoil	0.283	2.562		0.030	6.666		0.120	0.223		0.000	0.251	
OK	Samples	Topsoil	0.169	2.568		0.000	5.656	BS	0.034	0.227	BS	0.009	0.152	BS
OK	Samples	Subsoil	0.260	2.581	BS	0.064	6.410	BS	0.215	0.202	BS	0.010	0.222	BS
LinReg	EMI	Topsoil	0.042	2.812	-9.91	0.010	5.573	1.49	1.000	0.219	3.84	0.006	0.152	-0.11
LinReg	EMI	Subsoil	0.043	3.001	-14.01	1.000	6.654	-3.66	0.003	0.236	-14.43	1.000	0.226	-1.87
LinReg	γ-ray	Topsoil	1.000	2.842	-10.85	0.041	5.504	2.76	1.000	0.220	3.08	1.000	0.156	-2.62
LinReg	γ-ray	Subsoil	1.000	3.058	-15.60	0.032	6.609	-3.00	1.000	0.237	-14.75	0.030	0.223	-0.47
LinReg	VisNIR+XRF+TDR	Topsoil	0.130	2.606	-2.78	0.045	5.470	3.40	0.004	0.218	4.17	0.004	0.155	-2.03
LinReg	VisNIR+XRF+TDR	Subsoil	0.232	2.638	-2.17	0.008	6.685	-4.12	0.001	0.237	-14.62	1.000	0.229	-2.96
LinReg	Sentinel-2 + DEM covariates	Topsoil	0.307	2.383	6.34	0.047	5.689	-0.58	0.210	0.193	17.68	0.177	0.152	-0.34
LinReg	DEM covariates	Subsoil	0.017	3.005	-14.13	1.000	6.744	-4.96	1.000	0.237	-14.75	1.000	0.229	-2.96
LinReg	EMI + γ-ray + Sentinel-2 + DEM covariates	Topsoil	0.123	2.713	-6.63	0.076	5.493	2.97	0.073	0.224	1.28	0.186	0.157	-3.47
LinReg	EMI + γ-ray + DEM covariates	Subsoil	0.131	2.858	-9.70	0.032	6.609	-3.00	0.024	2.283	-91.15	0.058	0.221	0.35
LinReg	EMI + γ-ray + VisNIR+XRF+TDR + Sentinel-2 + DEM covariates	Topsoil	0.160	2.689	-5.76	0.156	5.140	10.03	0.078	0.209	8.49	0.130	0.169	-10.08
LinReg	EMI + γ-ray + VisNIR+XRF+TDR + DEM covariates	Subsoil	0.232	2.638	-2.17	0.099	6.454	-0.68	0.025	1.841	-89.02	0.058	0.221	0.35
PLSR	EMI	Topsoil	0.134	2.575	-1.60	0.108	5.212	8.50	0.015	0.213	6.66	0.108	0.143	5.92
PLSR	EMI	Subsoil	0.139	2.762	-6.56	0.083	6.287	1.95	0.094	0.220	-8.01	0.080	0.213	3.89
PLSR	γ-ray	Topsoil	0.076	2.659	-4.73	0.194	4.953	14.19	0.111	0.202	12.30	0.093	0.145	5.02
PLSR	γ-ray	Subsoil	0.086	2.846	-9.31	0.192	5.902	8.60	0.139	0.214	-5.66	0.187	0.201	10.51
PLSR	VisNIR+XRF+TDR	Topsoil	0.262	2.377	6.57	0.186	4.977	13.63	0.087	0.205	10.82	0.079	0.146	4.24
PLSR	VisNIR+XRF+TDR	Subsoil	0.366	2.370	8.89	0.125	6.142	4.36	0.071	0.222	-9.14	0.046	0.217	2.02
PLSR	EMI + γ-ray + Sentinel-2 + DEM covariates	Topsoil	0.306	2.305	9.93	0.311	4.580	23.49	0.283	0.182	25.04	0.304	0.127	19.84
PLSR	EMI + γ-ray + DEM covariates	Subsoil	0.368	2.367	9.05	0.246	5.701	12.43	0.253	0.200	1.28	0.282	0.189	17.58
PLSR	EMI + γ-ray + VisNIR+XRF+TDR + Sentinel-2 + DEM covariates	Topsoil	0.404	2.136	18.62	0.349	4.451	27.08	0.332	0.175	29.52	0.443	0.113	33.96
PLSR	EMI + γ-ray + VisNIR+XRF+TDR + DEM covariates	Subsoil	0.406	2.295	12.44	0.361	5.247	22.15	0.336	0.188	7.44	0.292	0.187	18.48
LinReg_RF	EMI + γ-ray + VisNIR+XRF+TDR + Sentinel-2 + DEM covariates	Topsoil	0.203	2.499	1.38	0.045	5.470	3.40	0.070	0.209	8.70	0.020	0.168	-9.43
PLSR_RF	EMI + γ-ray + VisNIR+XRF+TDR + Sentinel-2 + DEM covariates	Topsoil	0.345	2.239	13.13	0.218	4.880	15.89	0.178	0.194	16.79	0.178	0.138	10.30
LinReg_RF	EMI + γ-ray + VisNIR+XRF+TDR + DEM covariates	Subsoil	0.232	2.638	-2.17	0.080	6.471	-0.94	0.023	1.611	-87.46	0.058	0.221	0.35
PLSR_RF	EMI + γ-ray + VisNIR+XRF+TDR + DEM covariates	Subsoil	0.387	2.332	10.66	0.264	5.633	13.80	0.177	0.209	-3.48	0.226	0.196	13.26

Table 10: Model parameters and RI index for the CEC, clay, N, and SOC top and subsoil spatializations using sample-based, PSS covariates, DEM, and Sentinel-2 ancillary data. The modeling method is defined in the "Method" column, where IDW is inverse distance weighted, OK is ordinary kriging, and LinReg_RF and PLSR_RF stand for the modeling method using random forest for variables selection. BS indicates what modeling method for the sample-based group of data represents the baseline from which the RI index (increase in accuracy) is calculated.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020

research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 862695, and from the Tillämpningsklivet Precisionsodling RUN 2021–00020 Region Västra Götaland

Figure 14: Baselines (charts in the left) for topsoil (upper left) and subsoil (bottom left) datasets, and best model prediction (charts in the right) for topsoil (upper right) and subsoil (bottom right) datasets for CEC in the Ikizce municipality in the Ankara region in Turkey.

Except for the example with CEC, ordinary kriging threw the best estimations for choosing the baseline using the sample-based datasets. The modeling method with the highest increase in accuracy was the PLSR including all the ancillary variables together. Lower accuracy increases were associated with linear regression models using only one on-the-go sensor to model SOC and N. In particular, worse estimations with respect to the baseline were reached using LR and only one on-the-go sensor in the case of CEC and clay-subsoil. Utilizing PLSR with PSS point measurements threw a notable increase in accuracy compared to LR models. It is noteworthy that the estimation of soil parameters using PSS point measurements typically reaches the most accurate results; however, for this example, PCs were calculated for VNIR and XRF spectra to obtain raster layers that could be used as ancillary variables,

which represent a loss of information. For this reason, we recommend the use of SSL for the estimation of soil properties instead of spatializing PCs of the spectra.

Figure 15: Baselines (charts in the left) for topsoil (upper left) and subsoil (bottom left) datasets, and best model prediction (charts in the right) for topsoil (upper right) and subsoil (bottom right) datasets for clay in the Ikizce municipality in the Ankara region in Turkey.

The best model performance was reached using PLSR for modeling SOC in the topsoil using all the sensor's covariates, Sentinel-2 bands, and the fine-resolution DEM, whereas the best estimation for subsoil was found modeling the CEC with PLSR using all the sensor's covariates and the fine-resolution DEM. In contrast, the most considerable decreasing accuracy with respect to the baseline was found using LR after selecting the model variables (i.e., all ancillary variables were included in the selection process) using random forest to model N in the topsoil. For subsoil, the major accuracy decrease was

found in modeling N using LR with EMI and gamma-ray sensors, and the fine-resolution DEM. The digital soil maps for CEC, clay, N, and SOC in the topsoil and subsoil are represented in Figures 13 to 16.

Figure 16: Baselines (charts in the left) for topsoil (upper left) and subsoil (bottom left) datasets, and best model prediction (charts in the right) for topsoil (upper right) and subsoil (bottom right) datasets for N in the Ikizce municipality in the Ankara region in Turkey.

Figure 17: Baselines (charts in the left) for topsoil (upper left) and subsoil (bottom left) datasets, and best model prediction (charts in the right) for topsoil (upper right) and subsoil (bottom right) datasets for SOC in the Iikizce municipality in the Ankara region in Turkey.

5.4. Result: estimation of properties with VNIR and XRF, and cost-benefit index application

The cost-benefit analysis was applied to the PSS point measurements. Table 11 shows the model performance parameters for CEC, clay, N, and SOC together with the E index quantification. The E index summarizes the eligibility of a set of techniques and methods to obtain the best estimation with respect to the other options. In this case, the best estimation was obtained when modeling the four soil properties with VNIR compared to XRF and compared to the combination of VNIR and XRF. The

performance of all the models was, in general, notable except for the modeling of SOC and N with XRF. Best models were associated with the estimation of CEC.

Turkey, spectroscopy model performance and cost-effectiveness index						
Property	Sensor	R ²	RMSE	RPD	RPIQ	E_index
SOC	VNIR	0.42	0.17	1.32	1.72	0.8
SOC	XRF	0.10	0.21	1.6	1.41	0.3
SOC	VNIR+XRF	0.49	0.15	1.43	1.22	0.3
N	VNIR	0.39	0.2	1.29	1.79	0.6
N	XRF	0.07	0.24	1.05	1.45	0.3
N	VNIR+XRF	0.39	0.192	1.31	1.06	0.2
clay	VNIR	0.30	5.28	1.21	1.25	0.6
clay	XRF	0.48	4.56	1.4	1.45	0.4
clay	VNIR+XRF	0.52	4.32	1.47	0.68	0.4
CEC	VNIR	0.78	1.38	2.18	2.58	3.0
CEC	XRF	0.73	1.53	1.93	2.28	1.4
CEC	VNIR+XRF	0.82	1.21	2.46	1.6	1.2

Table 11: Cost-effectiveness analysis and model performance parameters of estimating soil properties using XRF and VNIR spectra measurements alone or in combination for the dataset in the Ikizce municipality in the Ankara region, Turkey. Dark green formatting indicates the most advantageous method, while light green indicates the least advantageous.

6. Dutch case study: Stratified Random and Random sampling (mixed strategy)

6.1. Site description

The study area is located at the UNIFARM experimental farm of Wageningen University and Research, the Netherlands, on fields bordering the Plassteeg and Dijkgraaf roads. Hence the site is referred to as ‘Plassteeg’ in this case study. The soil in the study area is generally sandy in texture with some thin clayey/loamy layers deeper down the profile and can be described as podzols or mollisols. The research site consists of two bordering fields, which measure approximately 8.3 ha in total. Both fields are under similar crop management, with full field crop rotation and management with regular agricultural crops and often cover crops in winter. Given their orientation, they are referred to as the northern and southern fields, separated by a ditch in the middle and bordered on two other sides by ditches as well. There is some ponding on the part of the fields and the fields are drained.

A (geographical) stratified sampling random design was applied to predefine 20 calibration locations across the two fields, assuming that there is a spatial variation of soil properties that could be captured with a reasonable spatial distribution. At the time of the sampling design, the sensing data was not available yet, hence the choice for this design. A random sampling design was applied to define 30 validation data points on the two fields to later validate the results (Figure 18). Soil samples were collected on the 17th of September 2021 from the topsoil (0-5 cm) at all sampling locations for the EJP SOIL internal STEROPES project to test the prediction capacity of satellite imagery with limited penetration depth. The soil samples were analyzed in the laboratory for the estimation of the SOM content using loss on ignition. In autumn 2023 new samples were taken at these points at 0-30 and 30-60 cm depth and analyzed in the lab for a broad spectrum of soil characteristics, specifically including soil properties mentioned in the just proposed EU Soil Monitoring Directive to understand the potential for using proximal and remote sensing for soil property estimation. For the purpose of this study, the 50 samples were in the end combined, and leave-one-out cross-validation was chosen due to the relatively low number of total samples.

Both fields were scanned with a CMD Mini-Explorer on Electrical Conductivity in December 2022 by Medusa Explorations BV. This yielded Dipole and EC bands, of which the 14 inverted EC bands are used

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020

research and innovation program under grant agreement N° 862695, and from Tillämpningsklivet Precisionsodling RUN 2021–00020 Region Västra Götaland

in this case study. The Southern field was also measured with a MS2000 gamma spectrometer and a 300 MHz ZONDe ground penetrating radar. The radar data are not used in this case study. the gamma spectrometer data has been analyzed by Medusa Explorations to concentrations of the gamma-ray nuclides ^{40}K , ^{238}U , ^{232}Th , and ^{137}Cs in Bq/kg. Sentinel 2 satellite imagery and UAV multispectral imagery was collected under bare soil conditions.

Figure 18: Calibration and validation sampling locations on the Plassteeg case study site near Wageningen, the Netherlands, consisting of two arable fields.

6.2. Data Preparation

In digital soil mapping (DSM), the spatial correlation of soil properties with the soil forming factors is used to predict spatial patterns of soil properties. In this study, the different bands of Sentinel 2 imagery (Red, Green, Blue, NIR, several Red Edge bands, SWIR) and the Copernicus DEM are used as covariate data for remote sensing data. All remote and proximal soil sensing and UAV data have been resampled to 5 meter resolution to even out any measurement noise and short-distance variation.

6.3. Exploratory data analysis and modeling

To get a general overview of the data several maps and graphs were made. For example the soil sample point data per soil property was plotted on a map and the average per field per depth layer was plotted per property to get an impression of differences between fields and depth layers.

To understand the dependencies between the available ancillary layers, a correlation matrix has been generated, Fig. 11. This shows among other things that layers per data source (EC, gamma-ray, satellite images per date) are often correlated. The matrix also allows to interpret and understand the direction and strength of the correlations, leading to an increased understanding of what the sensing layers could depict and with which soil properties they might correlate.

Plassteeg
depth 0-30 cm

Figure 19: Correlation matrix for Plassteeg field (Netherlands) of several soil properties with the available baselines (S2: Sentinel-2, Sat21: Satellite 2021, Sat20: Satellite 2020, ahn: Dutch elevation model based on LiDAR, PS: drone Multispectral (proximal), EMI: Electromagnetic Induction (proximal), ga: γ-ray spectrometer (proximal), EC: Electrical Conductivity (proximal), dp: dipole (proximal))

The baselines were established by calculating three basic interpolation methods, seen as references to which to compare a possible improvement in soil property prediction by adding soil sensing information: i) Global Mean, ii) inverse distance weighted, and iii) ordinary kriging. In the subsequent addition of sensing data layers, the accuracy of the modeling process was evaluated by comparing whether there was an increase or decrease of the RMSE and R^2 to the respective baseline.

When building the models, the 10 layers that show the highest correlations with the measured soil property are used. This prevents the building of models with too few levels of freedom (overfitting a model). These 10 best-performing layers are subsequently used to build linear models (LinReg). We used Akaike's information criteria to automatically select the optimal model. This method helps to select a model with not too many baselines but also a good fit. Other methods, such as regression kriging or random forest, require a reasonably large number of points to reliably estimate a semi-variogram or build the trees, e.g. 100 or 150 and more. These methods are, therefore, not applied.

Baselines and correlation matrices were calculated for C-anorganic, CEC, SOC, clay, sand, EC, K, SOM (2023), SOM (2021) in the topsoil and subsoil datasets. For each soil property, the added value of sensing data layers for the estimation of the soil property was tested in several test groups:

1. the proximal sensing layers are tested as a group;
2. the remote sensing layers are tested as a group;
3. with all the sensing layers together.

6.4. Results

As an example of the results, in Figure 20 and Figure 21, some of the results of the analysis for the Dutch Plassteeg field are depicted for SOM (Soil Organic Matter, measured in 2021). For this field, a high-resolution DEM and several proximal soil sensing layers are available, including a multispectral UAV image. From the figures, it is clear that the remote sensing layers or all sensing layers improve the predictions. Adding only the proximal soil sensing data does not improve the prediction as Inverse Distance Weighing performs better. However, neither of the models performed very well (As suggested by Chang et al., 2001, predictions of soil property models were considered poor for $RPD < 1.4$, moderate for $1.4 < RPD < 2$, and accurate for $RPD > 2$). The scatterplots of measurements against predictions also show the same poor to moderate correlation (Figure 21).

When evaluating the results of this comparison exercise, it should be considered that each of the baselines, or reference layers yields a different type of map or result. The increasing complexity of the interpolation also increases the spatial details visible on the maps. If these details are accurate and trustworthy, they can be judged using the provided metrics (R^2 , RPD) and expert judgment. If the additional detail is worth the additional cost should be evaluated using a cost-benefit exercise that was not done for this case study.

Figure 20: Coefficient of determination (R^2) and Ratio of Performance to Deviation for the models for SOM (2021) based on sample data and baseline data, site Plassteeg, the Netherlands.

Figure 21: Scatterplots for the sample models and the linear models for SOM (2021) (meas, %) against predicted (pred). The predictions were validated using a Leave One Out method.

For the following soil properties models were built as well:

- bact.bm, fungi.bm;
- CEC, Ec, Density;
- SIC, SOC, K, N-supply, N-Tot, P-AL, pH, SOM (2023), SOM (2021);
- Clay, Sand.

The accuracy of the models in terms of RPD was calculated for several (combinations of) data layers. Figure 22 gives an overview of the layer 0 to 30 cm. This figure shows that for CEC, EC, K, and SOM (2021), moderately accurate models could be built. The sensing layers used to build these models were Sentinel-2, satellite and also proximal data.

param	method	S2_R1	S2_R2	S2_R3	S2_R4	S2_G	S2_NIR	S2_SWIR1	S2_SWIR2	Sat20_I	Sat20_G	Sat21_R	ec3	emi_ec2	emi_ec5	R2	RMSE	RPD
Ec	LinReg ah ec ga em PS Sa S2	●	●					●		●			●	●	●	0.64	0.06	1.68
Ec	LinReg S2 Sa ah	●	●	●	●			●		●						0.56	0.06	1.52
CEC	LinReg S2 Sa ah		●		●	●	●		●	●		●				0.50	11.08	1.44
SOM2021	LinReg S2 Sa ah	●	●					●		●	●					0.48	0.51	1.40

Table 12: Overview of the moderately performing models and the selected data layers

Figure 22: Accuracy of the models (based on the RPD: Ratio of Performance to Deviation) for the models based on sample data and baseline data, site Plassteeg, the Netherlands (depth 0 till 30 cm)

The highest RPD for a baseline model has a value of 1.68. To build this model a set of data layers from different origins was used (satellite and proximal). In Figure 23 two maps are shown as an example 1) the samples alone interpolated by Inverse Distance Weighing and 2) several data layers used as input for a linear regression model. The figure shows similar patterns but also quite different local values and a different level of detail.

Figure 23: Models for EC based on a) samples only (IDW), b) based on baseline data from all sources (proximal and satellite), site Plassteeg, the Netherlands (depth 0 till 30 cm-sl) using linear regression.

7. Observations: Italian, Turkish, and Slovenian case studies

The survey campaigns in Italy, Turkey, and Slovenia combined six different PSS sensors in the field and in the laboratory to estimate multiple soil properties in the topsoil and the subsoil evaluating their performance individually and in multi-sensor systems. For modeling purposes, regular grids, treatment-based, and stratified random sampling strategies using ancillary available information of the

territory (i.e., Sentinel-2 imagery and Copernicus 30 m resolution DEM) were also evaluated. In addition, a cost-benefit framework analysis was applied in the three case studies to get insights into the eligibility of methods to get acceptable results.

In Italy, a total of 39 locations were sampled. Twenty locations were sampled at 0-30 and 30-60 cm depth in the western field, while in the rest of the locations, only topsoil samples were collected (two eastern fields). The total time invested was 6 hours with three operators. One operator was entirely dedicated to collecting data with the γ -ray and EMI sensors, and then collaborated in soil sampling using the auger. The total track distance collecting on-the-go sensor data was 7.05 Km by walking. Two operators collected TDR replicates and VNIR measurements.

In Slovenia, a total of 65 samples were collected from the topsoil (0-30 cm) and subsoil (both 30-60 and 60-90 cm, when possible). In this case, the sampling was split into three days due to the distance between the fields. On day one, in the Ljubljana LTE, the sampling took four hours to complete. On day two, both Moskanjci LTE fields were sampled in a time window of eight hours, and the survey of the Pivola field was performed on day three, which took only two hours to complete. Three operators were collaborating to carry on the activities. One operator was dedicated to performing the on-the-go surveys with the EMI and γ -ray sensors, while the other two operators were fully dedicated to taking measurements with the VNIR spectroradiometer, the TDR sensor, and collecting soil samples. The total track distance collecting on-the-go sensor data was 3.67 Km by walking.

In Turkey, a total of 82 soil samples were collected from 41 sampling locations. The total time invested in the survey was 8 hours with five operators. One operator was entirely dedicated to collecting data with the γ -ray and EMI sensors. The whole track distance to collect the on-the-go sensor data was 41.82 Km by walking. Three operators collected soil samples and TDR replicates. The last operator gave a hand in collecting the samplings but dedicated most of the time to collecting the VNIR spectroradiometer replicates.

During the surveys, the EM38-MK2 sensor was calibrated one or twice depending on the variability of soils. In the Slovenian study case, each field required an independent calibration due to the distance between fields. Each calibration took 10 minutes, approximately. The FieldScout TDR 150 required calibration using distilled water (5 minutes), while no calibration was required by the FieldScout TDR 300. No calibration was required for the γ -ray sensor. The spectroradiometers ASD Fieldspec Pro 3 and NeoSpectral Evolution 6500 needed the white reference calibration after 10-15 measurements (3-4 minutes each). The total time invested in calibration reached 40 minutes in the Slovenian case (NeoSpectral Evolution 6500), 30 minutes in the Italian case (ASD FieldSpec pro 3), and about 60 minutes were necessary in the Turkish case study (ASD FieldSpec pro 3). Considering the duration of batteries and the fact that the collection of spectra is more stable when the soil is sieved and dry, we recommend avoiding taking the VNIR sensor to the field if sample collection is expected. However, such a strategy does not allow for the calculation of the soil moisture effect that can be obtained by applying the EPO algorithm. In contrast, for spectral model-validation surveys (no sample collection expected), the use of portable VNIR spectroradiometers is highly recommended.

Based on the modeling results, we highly recommend using PLSR instead of LR to estimate soil properties independently of the applied technique. The cost of a five-sensor survey could be prohibitive even if that combination threw the most accurate models both for the topsoil and the subsoil. Based on the results of this example, we recommend using VNIR portable results for a more precise estimation in combination with an EMI sensor or γ -ray sensor. If on-the-go sensors are

unavailable, the Sentinel-2 imagery is an excellent option to produce digital soil maps. However, this option does not allow the estimation of soil properties in the subsoil.

8. Example from other EJP SOIL-related projects

The following are examples of demonstration sites for EJP SOIL projects linked to the Probedfield (see Fig. 1), where the same steps of the presented protocol were followed. This illustrates how results can differ between sites and different projects yet still be interpreted in a similar way.

8.1. Czech Republic Case study: Conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling

8.1.1. Site description

The study site included some agricultural lands located near Otnice which is a municipality and village in Vyškov District in the South Moravian Region of the Czech Republic. The sites mostly produce maize, potatoes, cereals and oilseed rape (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Study area in Czech Republic and the sampling points

8.1.2. Data preparation

This settlement study is conducted only for point measurement using the DSR technique.

A total of 106 soil samples were collected during a sampling campaign held in June and October 2022. Each sample was collected from the topsoil to the depth of 20 cm. Sampling was performed based on the stratified random strategy designed by the conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling (cLHS). The coordinates of each sampling point were determined using a GeoXM (Trimble Inc., Sunnyvale, California, USA) global positioning system (GPS) with 1 m spatial accuracy.

Samples were air-dried, ground, sieved (≤ 2 mm), and mixed before analysis. SOC content (%) of each soil sample was determined using the Walkley–Black method. The texture analysis is in progress using the pipette method.

ASD FieldSpec III Pro FR spectrometer (ASD Inc., Denver, Colorado, USA) was used within field and laboratory to record the spectral reflectance of the samples across the VNIR–SWIR range (350–2500 nm) by contacting a high-intensity probe. In the laboratory, soil samples were placed in 5.5 cm diameter petri dishes forming 2 cm layers of soil to avoid beam reflectance from the bottom of the dish. Samples were leveled off to obtain a flat surface for maximum light reflection and a high signal-to-noise ratio. All spectral readings were from the center of the samples. The spectrometer was calibrated using a white Spectralon™ (Lab-sphere, North Sutton, New Hampshire, USA) before the first scan and after every ten measurements.

The raw spectra were subjected to several pre-processing scenarios including: i) removing the artificial noise between 350–400 nm and 2451–2500 nm, caused by the device, ii) transformation of reflectance to absorbance via $\log(1/R)$ in which R is the reflectance spectra, iii) Savitzky-Golay smoothing, and iv) first derivative (FD) transformation to remove the baseline offset. Finally, the outliers were removed by applying the H-distance technique on the FD spectra and consequently, four samples were not consistent with the other observations and were removed from further processing.

SOC prediction models were developed using the partial least square regression (PLSR), random forest (RF), and support vector regression (SVR) algorithms developed on the FD-spectra and SOC.

8.1.3. Exploratory data analysis and modeling

Table 13 shows general statistics of the SOC content of the samples. Accordingly, the SOC content varied within the limits of 0.67% and 2.96% with an average of 1.82%. The SOC content of the samples followed the normal distribution (Figure 25).

Minimum	0.67
Maximum	2.96
Mean	1.82
Standard deviation	0.53
Range	2.29
Skewness	0.16
Kurtosis	-0.61
Coefficient of variation	0.29

Table 13: Descriptive statistics of samples' SOC content (%)

Figure 25: SOC content distribution histogram

8.1.4. Results

According to the modeling results on the field spectra (Table 14), RF showed the highest SOC prediction performance with RMSE = 0.22, $R^2 = 0.8$, and RPD = 2.27 on the validation data. PLSR models followed RF with RMSE = 0.24, $R^2 = 0.75$, and RPD = 2.03 on the validation dataset. A similar trend of performance can also be observed in the scatter diagrams (Figure 26).

Method	Dataset	ME	RMSE	R^2	LCCC	RPD	RPIQ
PLSR	Calibration	0	0.25	0.79	0.88	2.17	3.23
	Validation	-0.07	0.24	0.75	0.86	2.03	3.26
RF	Calibration	0	0.12	0.95	0.97	4.47	6.63
	Validation	-0.03	0.22	0.8	0.89	2.27	3.65
SVR	Calibration	-0.04	0.27	0.74	0.85	1.99	2.95
	Validation	-0.1	0.25	0.73	0.85	1.97	3.16

Table 14: SOC modeling results (field spectra)

Figure 26: Scatter diagrams comparing the observed and predicted SOC values (field spectra)

Variable importance plots of the RF models developed on field spectra are shown in Figure 27. Accordingly, the 30 highest influential predictor variables (spectral wavelengths) of each model are presented along with their percentage increase in mean squared error (%IncMSE) as a measure of variable importance obtained during the calibration of the models. As can be observed, visible and near-infrared bands were the most important variables that made an important contribution to the prediction capabilities of the developed model.

Figure 27: RF-based SOC prediction model’s variable importance plots (field spectra)

Method	Dataset	ME	RMSE	R ²	LCCC	RPD	RPIQ
PLSR	Calibration	0	0.16	0.91	0.95	3.3	4.9
	Validation	0	0.22	0.8	0.91	2.27	3.65
RF	Calibration	0	0.11	0.96	0.98	5.04	7.48
	Validation	-0.02	0.17	0.88	0.93	2.93	4.7
SVR	Calibration	-0.01	0.08	0.97	0.99	6.16	8.41
	Validation	0.04	0.29	0.74	0.85	1.98	3.28

Table 15: SOC modeling results (lab spectra)

Figure 28: Scatter diagrams comparing the observed and predicted SOC values (lab spectra)

Figure 29: RF-based SOC prediction model's variable importance plots (lab spectra)

9. 3D mapping options

The data and information gathered in the case studies described in chapters 4 to 6 regularly have collected both soil sensing and soil sample data at multiple depths and in a spatial context. Often, one or more maps in XY are made that represent a depth slice of the soil, for example, the average values between 0 and 30 cm depth or from 30 to 60 cm depth, using the available covariate or explanatory sensing data layers that are relevant for that depth layer. This can be considered as pseudo-3D or 2.5 D mapping.

Another possibility is to derive a 3D model based on 3D reference data using point-to-area or area-to-area interpolation. This is a very computationally intensive method and does not use the benefits of the available sensing data.

To create a 3D soil map using sensing data, the first step is to harmonize the support or footprint of the explanatory data layers that are to be used. For example, to resample or interpolate EC, satellite, γ -ray, Ground penetrating radar (GPR) data to the same grid in XYZ space. A challenge can be that not all data is available in the entire 3D space which means that either more information layers and

therefore a more complex geostatistical or machine learning model can be used at depth layers with more information layers, or the data sources that cannot provide data on all grid locations of the XYZ space are discarded. When this 3D explanatory data grid is created a model derived between the reference soil property values and the explanatory variables can be applied to the 3D space, just like in examples in the case study chapters of this report. Both the 3D interpolation and the derivation of the model between reference and explanatory variable can be done by techniques of simple interpolation and linear regression as by advanced non-linear machine learning methods.

The advantage is an increased understanding of the soil composition and potentially better-informed land management decisions by land managers.

Although for some of the case studies the data to test making a 3D map using sensing data is available, most of these data became available very late in the project, when it was not possible anymore to do a full analysis. This will be the objective of future work that some of the authors aim to continue with.

10. list of references

BRUS, D. ET AL. (2011). SAMPLING FOR VALIDATION OF DIGITAL SOIL MAPS. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF SOIL SCIENCE. 62. 394 - 407. [10.1111/j.1365-2389.2011.01364.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.2011.01364.x).

CHANG, CHENG-WEN ET AL. (2001). NEAR-INFRARED REFLECTANCE SPECTROSCOPY–PRINCIPAL COMPONENTS REGRESSION ANALYSES OF SOIL PROPERTIES. SOIL SCIENCE SOCIETY OF AMERICA JOURNAL. 65. 480-490. [10.2136/sssaj2001.652480x](https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2001.652480x).

GRANGER CWJ, & RAMANATHAN R (1984) IMPROVED METHODS OF COMBINING FORECASTS. JOURNAL OF FORECASTING 3(2), 197–204. DOI:10.1002/FOR.3980030207

LI, S. ET AL. (2022). THE COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF REFLECTANCE SPECTROSCOPY FOR ESTIMATING SOIL ORGANIC CARBON. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF SOIL SCIENCE, 73(1), E13202. [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.1111/EJSS.13202](https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13202)

METZGER, K.; ET. AL (2024). PREDICTION ACCURACY OF SOIL CHEMICAL PARAMETERS BY FIELD- AND LABORATORY-OBTAINED VIS-NIR SPECTRA AFTER EXTERNAL PARAMETER ORTHOGONALIZATION. SENSORS 2024, 24, 3556. [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.3390/s24113556](https://doi.org/10.3390/s24113556)

STENBERG, B. ET. AL (2024). D5.1 PROBEFIELD: BEST PRACTICE PROTOCOL FOR FIELD SPECTROSCOPY AND ASSESSMENT BY SOIL SPECTRAL LIBRARY BASED CALIBRATIONS (VERSIONE 1). ZENODO. [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14150972](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14150972)

